

Examining Measurement Invariance and Differences in Age Cohorts on the Supports Intensity Scale–Children’s Version–Catalan Translation

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Abstract

Data from 949 children and adolescents with intellectual disability ages 5 to 16 for whom the Supports Intensity Scale–Children’s Version–Catalan Translation was completed was used, in combination with data from the U.S. standardization sample, to examine measurement invariance and latent differences in the Catalonian sample. Results suggest that the same set of items can be used to measure support needs across U.S. and Catalonia samples and that there are age-related differences in support needs in the Catalonia sample, particularly between children ages 5 to 10 and 11 to 16 years of age. This differs from findings with the U.S. sample, where differences were found in a greater number of age cohorts. Implications for future research and practice are discussed.

Key Words: *intellectual disability; support needs assessment; cross-cultural; Catalan Translation*

Support needs is a psychological construct, defined as “the pattern and intensity of support a person requires to participate in activities associated with typical human functioning” (Thompson et al., 2009, p. 135). It is assumed that support needs emerge when people experience a mismatch between their personal competencies and the demands of the environments in which they participate. In the intellectual disability (ID) field, a growing emphasis has been placed on assessing support needs to build systems of support that enhance personal functioning and quality of life. This focus has emerged because of the growing adoption of a social-ecological understanding of disability (Schalock et al., 2010; World Health Organization, 2001), and a movement away from deficit-based approaches to assessment and understanding ID. Addressing support needs with a strengths-based approach focuses on promoting valued outcomes, including the supports necessary to participate in inclusive, community environments across the lifespan.

Assessment tools, such as the Supports Intensity Scale–Adult Version (SIS–A; Thompson et al., 2004; Thompson et al., 2015) and the Supports Intensity Scale–Children’s Version (SIS–C; Thompson et al., 2016), have been developed and are increasingly being adopted to guide supports planning for children and adults with intellectual and developmental disabilities. The original version of the SIS was published in 2004 and normed for adults with intellectual disability ages 16 to 64 years. This tool has been translated into over a dozen languages and used to influence supports planning and resource allocation throughout the world (American Association on Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities [AAIDD], 2014). The SIS–C was more recently developed and published to address the demand for support needs assessment tools for use with children. It was developed and normed with a U.S. sample of children with intellectual disability ages 5 to 16 years. Translations have already been undertaken (Verdugo et al., 2016), and a process

developed to create international norms for translated versions of the scale leveraging the large U.S. norming sample (Seo, Shaw, Shogren, Lang, & Little, in press). This is particularly important for translated versions of the SIS-C as the standardization sample for developing norms for the SIS-C was stratified based on age cohorts (5–6, 7–8, 9–10, 11–12, 13–14, and 15–16 year olds), then on level of intellectual functioning (i.e., mild, moderate, severe/profound) within each age cohort as it was assumed that support needs would be strongly correlated with age, with younger children showing more intense support needs compared to older children, irrespective of disability status. Research with the U.S. standardization sample confirmed the influence of age, finding differences in latent means based on age across support need domains assessed on the SIS-C (i.e., Home Living, Community and Neighborhood, School Participation, School Learning, Health and Safety, Social, and Advocacy Activities). This led to the creation of separate norms for each of the age cohorts (Thompson et al., 2016). However, different findings were obtained when developing norms for the SIS-C Spanish Translation of the scale. In a standardization sample collected in Spain with the same stratification plan, it was found that measurement invariance could be established, but when examining age-related differences, several age cohorts could be collapsed. Differences were concentrated between 6 to 10 and 11 to 16 year olds, and two (rather than six) sets of norms were developed (Verdugo et al., 2016). It was hypothesized that there may be cultural factors related to the structure of the Spanish schooling system as well as the greater homogeneity of the Spanish population that may have led to these findings.

As additional translations and norm development activities are undertaken in other cultural contexts, it will be important to further examine cultural differences, particularly age-related differences in latent support need domains (i.e., Home Living, Community and Neighborhood, School Participation, School Learning, Health and Safety, Social, and Advocacy Activities) within translated versions of the scale. The purpose of this article, therefore is to examine the measurement properties of the SIS-C Catalan Translation, providing information on similarities and differences in findings from the original, English version of the SIS-C and the SIS-C Spanish Translation.

Catalonia is an autonomous community in northeastern Spain with a population of approximately 7.5 million people. Spain is comprised of different nations and cultures from the late Middle Ages which came together as a single country. Territorially and politically, Spain is comprised of 17 autonomous communities each with their own parliament and government, and Catalonia is one of these communities. Although Spanish is far and away the dominant language in most of Spain, several of the autonomous communities have co-official languages, including Catalonia. Catalonia is unique in that in most of the communities with co-official languages, Spanish is the dominant language. However, in Catalonia, this is not the case. Catalan, the Catalonia language, is spoken in the home, school, business community, and throughout people's daily lives. And the differences between the Catalonia and the other regions of Spain are not limited to language, but also the culture, values, and even some aspects of civil law. Hargreaves (2000) describes the Catalan concept of *fet diferencial* (roughly translated as “distinguishing feature”) as “as a set of popular beliefs as to what constitution the Catalan character” (p. 22). Catalans celebrate their uniqueness and have historically (and currently) considered Catalonia to be a distinct and separate culture from the rest of Spain. This is reflected in the ongoing self-governance of Catalonia, which has been maintained despite pressures to change. Catalonia has distinct education, social services, and health programs from Spain, leading to a unique Catalonia macrosystem, distinct from Spain. This necessitates the translation of tools, such as the SIS-C into Catalan, and examination of the properties of translated versions of the assessment.

Given these issues, the purpose of the present study was to examine the following research questions:

1. Do the seven support needs domain constructs measured by the SIS-C Catalan Translation (Home Life, Community and Neighborhood, School Participation, School Learning, Health and Safety, Social, and Advocacy Activities) have construct comparability across six age groups of Catalan children and youth with intellectual disability (5–6, 7–8, 9–10, 11–12, 13–14, and 15–16 years; i.e., can the same items be used across age groups)?

2. Do Catalan children and youth with intellectual disability in the six age groups have different latent means for each of the seven support needs domains?
3. Do Catalan children and youth with intellectual disability in the six age groups have different latent variances in each of the seven support needs domains?

Methods

Samples

Participants consisted of 949 children and adolescents with intellectual disability from the SIS-C Catalan Translation standardization sample (5–16 year olds). To generate the Catalonian normative sample, data was collected throughout the four main regions of Catalonia (Barcelona, Girona, Lleida, and Tarragona) with the support of the Educational Administration of the Government of Catalonia. The sample was roughly distributed according to the population distribution across the four regions, with Barcelona the largest proportion of the sample (57%), followed by Tarragona (16%), Girona (16%) and Lledia (10%). Barcelona is considered an urban and suburban region with high population density, whereas the other regions are more rural except for their capitals. Information about the SIS-C and the standardization process was sent to all schools in each region, including special schools for students with disabilities and “mainstreamed” schools where students with and without disabilities are educated. In accordance with the distribution of where students with intellectual disability are educated in Catalonia, approximately one third of the sample came from special schools and two thirds from mainstreamed schools. In each school in Catalonia, there are Psychological Assessment and Counseling Teams comprised of psychologists, teachers, and social workers whose primary role is to support the early detection of developmental disorders, address difficulties and challenges faced by students, lead the assessment of students’ special education needs, and prepare and monitor the individualized education program (IEP) of students. The Psychological Assessment and Counseling Teams, together with the Principal of the school, identified students who were eligible for the SIS-C based on the presence of intellectual disability.

As described previously, because it was assumed that age is related to support needs as evidenced by Shogren et al. (2015), the SIS-C Catalan Task Force collected their standardization sample to parallel that of the U.S. standardization sample. First the sample was stratified by 2-year age groups: 5–6, 7–8, 9–10, 11–12, 13–14, and 15–16 year olds. Next, when possible, the norming sample was further stratified within age groups by level of intellectual functioning (i.e., mild, $IQ > 55$; moderate, $IQ 40-55$; severe/profound, $IQ < 40$) to represent disability-related characteristics. However, in Catalonia it is not compulsory for schools to have IQ and adaptive behavior scores in student records. Eligibility for special education services is based on need not on results of IQ and adaptive behavior testing, and for that reason many schools were not able to provide this information. However, Psychological Assessment and Counseling Teams teams worked to select students that represented the range of students with intellectual disability.

Because of the lack of information available on this variable in the Catalonian context, 519 (54.7%) participants had incomplete information on intellectual functioning. Table 1 provides the distributed sample size across the 18 sampling cells (six age bands \times three levels of intellectual functioning) based on available data. The majority of the Catalan standardization sample

Table 1
Distributed Sample Size for Age Groups and Intellectual Functioning

Age Cohort	Mild	Moderate	Severe/Profound	Total
5–6	39	33	23	95
7–8	43	41	18	102
9–10	49	37	18	104
11–12	52	34	19	105
13–14	33	18	14	65
15–16	15	19	14	48
Total	231	182	106	519

Note. Mild intellectual disability group - $IQ > 55$; Moderate intellectual disability group - $IQ 40-55$; Severe/Profound intellectual disability group - $IQ < 40$. Intellectual functioning data was missing for 430 participants. Adapted from the *SIS-C Catalan Users’ Manual* by A. L. Adam, D. Simó, J. Mas, M. Dalmau, C., Giné, H. Seo, L. A. Shaw, K. A. Shogren, and J. R. Thompson, 2016. Technical properties of the *Supports Intensity Scale - Children’s Version - Catalan Translation*.

were male (64%; $n = 604$) and Table 2 provides further information on participants' demographic characteristics.

The SIS-C Catalan standardization sample was linked to the SIS-C U.S. normative sample ($n = 4,015$; 5–16 year olds) to test measurement invariance and differences in latent parameters so as to generate norms for the SIS-C Catalan. This allowed for a smaller sample size to be collected for the Catalan sample as the inclusion of the U.S. normative data was to stabilize parameter estimates in the norm-generating models with a large U.S. sample size and its established SIS-C measurement properties. Further information is provided on the technical reasons for this linking in Seo, Shaw, et al. (in press), where procedures and findings related to the norming the SIS-C Spanish Translation are described in detail. The same approach described by Seo, Shaw, et al. (in press) was undertaken in the present investigation to examine age-related latent differences on support needs constructs in the Catalan sample and to address the implications for generating norms for the Catalan Translation. Further details on U.S. normative sample are provided in Thompson et al. (2016) and on age-invariance testing in the U.S. normative sample in Shogren et al. (2015).

Supports Intensity Scale–Children's Version Catalan Translation

As mentioned previously, the SIS-C was developed to measure the pattern and intensity of support needs of children and youth with intellectual disability ages 5 to 16. The SIS-C consists of two sections: (a) Exceptional Medical and Behavioral Needs and (b) Supports Needs Index Scale. The Exceptional Medical and Behavioral Needs section evaluates support that is needed to manage multiple medical conditions including respiratory care, feeding assistance, skin care, and other exceptional medical care, as well as challenging behaviors including externally directed destructiveness, self-directed destructiveness, sexual, and other exceptional behavioral concerns. Items in the Exceptional Medical and Behavioral Needs section are not included in the standardized portion of the scale, but are assessed for use by planning teams as it is assumed (and has been confirmed by research; see Seo, Shogren, Wehmeyer, Little, & Palmer, 2017) that the presence of these issues will influence support needs. The

Table 2
Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Male	604	63.6
Female	345	36.4
Age Group		
5–6	191	20.1
7–8	192	20.2
9–10	181	19.1
11–12	184	19.4
13–14	123	13.0
15–16	78	8.2
Student's Intelligence Level		
55–70 or Mild	231	24.3
40–55 or Moderate	182	19.2
25–39 or Severe	76	8.0
< 25 or Profound	30	3.2
Missing	430	45.3
Student's Adaptive Behavior Level		
Mild	93	9.8
Moderate	93	9.8
Severe	97	10.2
Profound	79	8.3
Missing	587	61.9
Student's Home Residence		
Family Home	924	97.4
Foster Family Home	10	1.1
Small Group Home (< 7 residents)	7	0.7
Residence	3	0.3
Other residential facility	5	0.5
Primary Language		
Catalan	392	41.3
Spanish	418	44.0
Catalan + Spanish	68	7.2
Other	59	6.2
Missing	12	1.3

Note. Adapted from the *SIS-C Catalan Users' Manual* by A. L. Adam, D. Simó, J. Mas, M. Dalmau, C., Giné, H. Seo, L. A. Shaw, K. A. Shogren, and J. R. Thompson, 2016. Technical properties of the *Supports Intensity Scale – Children's Version - Catalan Translation*.

second section, Supports Needs Index Scale, is the standardized portion of the scale and includes items organized into seven life activity domains: Home Life, Community and Neighborhood,

School Participation, School Learning, Health and Safety, Social, and Advocacy Activities. Items from these seven life domains are rated on three dimensions: type of support (e.g., amount of physical assistance), daily support time (hours and minutes devoted to support), and frequency of support (how often support is needed). Each of the three dimensions is rated on a 5-point scale. Averaged ratings across the three domains are used to calculate subscale standard scores and a composite standard score (i.e., SIS–C Support Needs Index score).

The SIS–C Catalan Translation, along with other SIS–C international translations (e.g., SIS–C Spanish Translation, SIS–C Italian Translation), was developed through rigorous translation strategies described by Tassé and Thompson (2010). The translation process consists of the following three steps:

1. The first committee is divided into two teams, with each team having a professional translator and bilingual content expert. Each team independently translates items on the SIS–C, and a joint meeting is convened to compare translations. Disparities are addressed to create the *Preliminary Translation*.
2. The *Preliminary Translation* is provided to a second committee of bilingual content experts and translators. This group verifies the quality and/or accuracy of the *Preliminary Translation* by comparing it to the original, English version of the SIS–C. The two committees then meet to discuss differences and reach consensus, at which point the *Pretest Translation* is finalized.
3. The *Pretest Translation* is piloted with a group of potential SIS–C Catalan translation users who are asked to provide feedback through focus groups and Likert scale ratings. Final edits are made based on this feedback to create the *Final Translation*.

The Catalan SIS–C Task Force used the *Final Translation* to collect data for the SIS–C Catalan Translation normative sample.

Data Analysis

A series of multiple-group mean and covariance structures (MACS; Little, 1997) confirmatory factor analyses (CFAs) were conducted to address the three research questions. Due to the relatively small Catalan sample size (i.e., sample size per

Catalan age group ranged between 78 and 192), we leveraged the U.S. normative sample to stabilize the parameter estimates of the Catalan data. To briefly summarize the data analysis process, we combined the U.S. data ($n = 4,015$) with the Catalan data ($n = 949$) and performed measurement invariance testing across 12 age groups (6 U.S. groups + 6 Catalan groups divided by the age bands referenced previously), and tested latent differences in means and variances of Catalan support needs constructs while letting the U.S. latent parameters be freely estimated. The effects-coding method of identification (Little, Slegers, & Card, 2006) was used to scale the model so that estimated parameters reflected the metric of observed SIS–C scores. Mplus 7.2 (Muthén & Muthén, 1998–2012) was used for MACS CFA data analyses with maximum likelihood estimation.

Premodeling process. The Catalan SIS–C data was inspected for missing values prior to the MACS CFA. The amount of missing responses on any one question ranged from 0 missing to 3 missing (0.00%–0.32%). Eight questions in the Catalan SIS–C data had values that were out of range (> 4 on a scale of 0–4), so those illegal values were converted to missing values. To recover missing data, the imputed U.S. data was combined with the Catalan data for a single imputation at the item level. R 3.2.0 (R Core Team, 2015) and the mice package (van Buuren & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011) with predictive mean matching was used to impute the missing data. (See Seo, Little, Shogren, and Lang [2016] for more details on missing data handling for the data from the U.S. standardization sample.) The choice was made to combine the U.S. and Catalan data for imputation based on the assumption that the samples are from the same larger population of children with intellectual disability, and that the inclusion of country variables in the predictive mean matching imputation process would address country-related differences. After missing observations were imputed, we generated parcels (i.e., the parsimonious representations of indicators; the averages in our case) using guidelines provided by Seo et al. (2016). Parcels result in higher reliability (Little, Cunningham, Shahar, & Widaman, 2002; Little, Rhemtulla, Gibson, & Schoemann, 2013) and mimic in practice how the SIS–C was designed to be scored. After parcels were generated, each question was examined for

univariate and bivariate normality, and all values were determined to be within acceptable ranges (Kline, 2011).

Research question 1–Construct comparability across U.S. and Catalan age groups. Establishing the construct comparability (i.e., that the same set of indicators can be used) across subgroups was tested at three sequential invariance levels (Brown, 2015). First, configural invariance test imposed the equivalent patterns of freed and fixed parameters across six U.S. and six Catalan age groups. Configural models were evaluated by examining a set of fit indices, χ^2 , root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), the comparative fit index (CFI), and the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), which is also known as the non-normed fit index, and standardized root mean square residual (SRMR). A model with a large sample size will almost always have a χ^2 that indicates significantly poor fit, but such models can often have other fit indices that indicate acceptable fit (Little, 2013). Acceptable values for RMSEA are $\sim .08$ or smaller, CFI and TLI greater than $.90$ and SRMR that is approximately $.08$ or smaller. As recommended by Little (2013), these fit indices are evaluated as a set rather than singly when determining acceptable model fit. Next, the weak invariance test constrained factor loadings equal across U.S. and Catalan age groups. Establishing weak invariance is a necessary condition for between-group comparisons of linear associations among the latent variables. Last, the strong invariance test imposed equality constraints on indicator intercepts across the 12 age groups. The change in CFI less than or equal to $.01$ (Cheung & Rensvold, 2002) was used as a criterion to determine the tenability of equality constraints when moving from a less constrained model to the next model (i.e., configural to weak or weak to strong).

Research question 2–Differences in latent means across Catalan age groups. Using a series of nested χ^2 tests, we performed the sequential latent mean comparisons for each latent support needs domain. It should be noted that, in the 12-group model, equality constraints were only placed on latent means from six Catalan age groups whereas the six U.S. latent means were freely estimated (see Seo, Shaw, et al. [in press] for the rationale for freeing U.S. latent parameters). For example, we imposed the equality constraints on Social domain latent means for ages 5–6 and 7–8 in the Catalan data. In the meantime, all the U.S. latent means were freed. Then, we proceeded

with a nested χ^2 test comparing this model to the strong invariance model (Kline, 2011; Little, 2013). When results showed that Social latent means could be equated between the 5–6 and 7–8 Catalan age groups, we placed further equality constraint on a social latent mean of the 9–10 Catalan age group. This model was then compared against its previous model (model with equality constraints on Social means of 5–6 and 7–8 age groups vs. model with equality constraints on Social means of 5–6, 7–8, and 9–10 age groups). This process was replicated across all six age groups and support needs constructs to generate the age groups that significantly differed from each other in each support need domain.

Research question 3–Differences in latent variances across Catalan age groups. To address Research Question 3, we mirrored the analytic procedure used to test latent mean differences except for (a) equality constraints were placed on latent variances and (b) instead of the strong invariance model used to initiate a sequential test in Research Question 2, we used the final latent mean model for each domain (see A6, B6, C6, D6, E6, F6, and G6 in Table 4) as the baseline model when comparing the nested models for the given latent variances. For instance, the final Social domain mean model was employed as a starting model to test Social variance. Aside from these two differences, the analytic procedure remained the same as latent mean comparisons conducted for Research Question 2.

Results

Research Question 1–Construct Comparability Across U.S. and Catalan Age Groups

As shown in Table 3, the configural invariance model fit was acceptable: $\chi^2(2016) = 6915.761$, RMSEA = $.077$ (90% CI: $.075$ – $.079$), CFI = $.965$, TLI = 0.956 , and SRMR = $.026$. Both weak and strong invariance tests were passed based on the changes in CFI (Δ CFI = $.003$ between configural and weak invariance models; Δ CFI = $.004$ between weak and strong invariance models). This indicates that equality constraints imposed on factor loadings and indicator intercepts, respectively, did not worsen model fit; the established construct comparability suggests that the support needs constructs can be defined using the same

Table 3
Fit Indices for the Nested Sequence in the Multiple-Group Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Model	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	RMSEA	RMSEA, 90% CI	CFI	TLI	Constraint Tenable
Configural	6915.761	2016	.00	.077	.075–.079	.965	0.956	—
Weak	7359.426	2170	.00	.076	.074–.078	.962	0.956	Yes
Strong	8191.447	2324	.00	.078	.076–.080	.958	0.954	Yes

indicators across the age bands (5–16 year old) and between two contexts (U.S. and Catalan).

Research Question 2–Differences in Latent Means Across Catalan Age Groups

Table 4 provides the results from the sequential tests that compared latent means across the Catalan age groups. Each of the Home Life, Community and Neighborhood, School Participation, School Learning, Health and Safety, and Social domains tended to have similar latent means within the younger age group (5–10 year olds) or within the older age group (11–16 year olds). These empirical results support that there is a conceptual difference between younger and older age groups when understanding support needs of Catalan children with intellectual disability. Although the last construct, Advocacy domain, appeared to have the equivalent means across six age groups, when we simultaneously imposed two sets of equality constraints on the Advocacy domain (i.e., one set for 5–10 and another set for 11–16 age group), the tenability of these equality constraints was established (See G6 in Table 4). Based on the consistent results that found the age break point between 10 and 11 years across support needs domains, we made a theoretical decision to maintain two sets of equality constraints across all seven domains to better represent age impact on support needs of Catalan children and youth with intellectual disability.

Research Question 3–Differences in Latent Variances Across Catalan Age Groups

Using the final latent mean model (see A6, B6, C6, D6, E6, F6, and G6 in Table 4) for each construct as a baseline model, differences in latent variances and corresponding standard deviations (i.e., the squared root of given variances) were compared across Catalan age groups. As shown in

Table 5, each domain had equivalent variances and standard deviations. Latent means, variances, and standard deviations in younger (5–10 year olds) and older (11–16 year olds) are provided in Table 6.

Discussion

The results of this study suggest two primary findings. First, for the SIS–C Catalan, the same items and measurement structure (i.e., seven support need domains measured by multiple item-level indicators) used on the SIS–C when normed in the U.S. context can be used to assess support needs in children ages 5 to 16 in the Catalonian context. Establishing measurement equivalence or construct comparability is a critical and necessary first step in ensuring that the same constructs can and are being measured across age groups within and across cultures (Lee, Preacher, & Little, 2010; Little, 1997). It also confirms the role of the seven support needs domains measured on the SIS–C (Home Life, Community and Neighborhood, School Participation, School Learning, Health and Safety, and Social) across cultural contexts. Standard guidelines in cross-cultural research suggest that if a majority of the items are invariant in measurement models, then there are universal aspects of the latent construct, and these universal aspects were explored in the structural models (Lee et al., 2010). This study confirmed these universal aspects of the support need constructs across the U.S. and Catalonian sample (Research Question 1), a necessary first step to using the U.S. norming sample to create norms for the Catalan sample, and to conduct latent different testing within the Catalan sample (Research Questions 2 and 3) cross-cultural comparisons.

In examining the structural models and differences within the age bands represented in the Catalonia sample, there latent differences

Table 4
Sequential Latent Mean Tests Across Catalan Age Groups in Each Support-Need Construct

Model	Model Name	χ^2	df	Model Comparison	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p	Constraint Tenable
Strong invariance model (Subscale scores)	M1	8191.45	2324	—	—	—	—	—
Home Life Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)	A1	8192.61	2325	M1 vs. A1	1.16	1	0.282	Yes
5-6 = 7-8	A2	8200.36	2326	A1 vs. A2	7.75	1	0.005	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	A3	8242.64	2327	A2 vs. A3	42.28	1	0.000	No
11-12 = 13-14	A4	8192.74	2325	M1 vs. A4	1.29	1	0.255	Yes
11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	A5	8193.92	2326	A4 vs. A5	1.17	1	0.279	Yes
[5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10] [11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16]	A6	8202.83	2328	M1 vs. A6	11.38	4	0.023	Yes
Community and Neighborhood Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)	B1	8191.46	2325	M1 vs. B1	0.01	1	0.924	Yes
5-6 = 7-8	B2	8192.11	2326	B1 vs. B2	0.65	1	0.420	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	B3	8206.72	2327	B2 vs. B3	14.61	1	0.000	No
11-12 = 13-14	B4	8191.47	2325	M1 vs. B4	0.02	1	0.877	Yes
11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	B5	8192.71	2326	B4 vs. B5	1.24	1	0.266	Yes
[5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10] [11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16]	B6	8193.37	2328	M1 vs. B6	1.92	4	0.750	Yes
School Participation Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)	C1	8191.47	2325	M1 vs. C1	0.02	1	0.874	Yes
5-6 = 7-8	C2	8195.92	2326	C1 vs. C2	4.45	1	0.035	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	C3	8221.98	2327	C2 vs. C3	26.05	1	0.000	No
11-12 = 13-14	C4	8191.81	2325	M1 vs. C4	0.36	1	0.547	Yes
11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	C5	8193.52	2326	C4 vs. C5	1.71	1	0.191	Yes
[5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10] [11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16]	C6	8198.00	2328	M1 vs. C6	6.55	4	0.162	Yes
School Learning Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)	D1	8192.44	2325	M1 vs. D1	0.99	1	0.319	Yes
5-6 = 7-8	D2	8192.48	2326	D1 vs. D2	0.04	1	0.850	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	D3	8202.22	2327	D2 vs. D3	9.74	1	0.002	No

(Table 4 continued)

Table 4
Continued

Model	Model Name	χ^2	df	Model Comparison	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p	Constraint Tenable
	11-12 = 13-14	8191.55	2325	M1 vs. D4	0.10	1	0.746	Yes
	11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	8192.10	2326	D4 vs. D5	0.55	1	0.459	Yes
	[5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10] [11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16]	8193.13	2328	M1 vs. D6	1.69	4	0.793	Yes
Health and Safety Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)								
	5-6 = 7-8	8191.45	2325	M1 vs. E1	0.01	1	0.933	Yes
	5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	8193.73	2326	E1 vs. E2	2.27	1	0.131	Yes
	5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	8205.74	2327	E2 vs. E3	12.02	1	0.001	No
	11-12 = 13-14	8192.65	2325	M1 vs. E4	1.20	1	0.273	Yes
	11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	8192.86	2326	E4 vs. E5	0.21	1	0.647	Yes
	[5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10] [11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16]	8195.14	2328	M1 vs. E6	3.69	4	0.449	Yes
Social Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)								
	5-6 = 7-8	8191.59	2325	M1 vs. F1	0.15	1	0.702	Yes
	5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	8193.42	2326	F1 vs. F2	1.83	1	0.176	Yes
	5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	8212.30	2327	F2 vs. F3	18.88	1	0.000	No
	11-12 = 13-14	8193.09	2325	M1 vs. F4	1.64	1	0.200	Yes
	11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	8193.50	2326	F4 vs. F5	0.41	1	0.520	Yes
	[5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10] [11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16]	8195.48	2328	M1 vs. F6	4.03	4	0.402	Yes
Advocacy Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)								
	5-6 = 7-8	8191.47	2325	M1 vs. G1	0.02	1	0.882	Yes
	5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	8191.94	2326	G1 vs. G2	0.47	1	0.495	Yes
	5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	8196.10	2327	G2 vs. G3	4.16	1	0.041	Yes
	5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14	8196.38	2328	G3 vs. G4	0.28	1	0.599	Yes
	5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	8196.92	2329	G4 vs. G5	0.55	1	0.459	Yes
	[5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10] [11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16]	8194.52	2328	M1 vs. G6	3.07	4	0.546	Yes

Note. RMSEA, CFI, and TLI did not change from the Strong model in Table 3, or changed by less than .001 across all estimated models.

Table 5
Sequential Latent Variance Tests Across Catalan Age Groups in Each Support-Need Construct

Model	Model Name	χ^2	df	Model Comparison	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δ	df	p	Constraint Tenable
Home Life Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)									
Final Latent Mean Model									
5-6 = 7-8	FA	8202.83	2328	—	—	—	—	—	—
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	A1	8204.08	2329	FA vs. A1	1.25	1	0.263	0.263	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	A2	8205.31	2330	A1 vs. A2	1.23	1	0.267	0.267	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14	A3	8205.47	2331	A2 vs. A3	0.17	1	0.684	0.684	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	A4	8206.47	2332	A3 vs. A4	0.99	1	0.319	0.319	Yes
	A5	8208.69	2333	A4 vs. A5	2.23	1	0.136	0.136	Yes
Community and Neighborhood Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)									
Final Latent Mean Model									
5-6 = 7-8	FB	8193.37	2328	—	—	—	—	—	—
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	B1	8194.77	2329	FA vs. B1	1.40	1	0.236	0.236	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	B2	8195.24	2330	B1 vs. B2	0.47	1	0.492	0.492	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14	B3	8195.33	2331	B2 vs. B3	0.09	1	0.764	0.764	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	B4	8196.84	2332	B3 vs. B4	1.51	1	0.219	0.219	Yes
	B5	8201.62	2333	B4 vs. B5	4.77	1	0.029	0.029	Yes
School Participation Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)									
Final Latent Mean Model									
5-6 = 7-8	FC	8198.00	2328	—	—	—	—	—	—
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	C1	8199.53	2329	FC vs. C1	1.53	1	0.216	0.216	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	C2	8200.02	2330	C1 vs. C2	0.49	1	0.485	0.485	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14	C3	8200.68	2331	C2 vs. C3	0.67	1	0.414	0.414	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	C4	8203.07	2332	C3 vs. C4	2.39	1	0.122	0.122	Yes
	C5	8203.87	2333	C4 vs. C5	0.80	1	0.372	0.372	Yes
School Learning Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)									
Final Latent Mean Model									
5-6 = 7-8	FD	8193.13	2328	—	—	—	—	—	—
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	D1	8195.58	2329	FD vs. D1	2.44	1	0.118	0.118	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	D2	8203.50	2330	D1 vs. D2	7.92	1	0.005	0.005	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14	D3	8204.13	2331	D2 vs. D3	0.64	1	0.426	0.426	Yes
	D4	8205.79	2332	D3 vs. D4	1.66	1	0.198	0.198	Yes

(Table 5 continued)

Table 5
 Continued

Model	Model Name	χ^2	df	Model Comparison	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	p	Constraint Tenable
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	D5	8210.12	2333	D4 vs. D5	4.33	1	0.037	Yes
Health and Safety Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)								
Final Latent Mean Model								
5-6 = 7-8	FE	8195.14	2328	—	—	—	—	—
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	E1	8195.99	2329	FE vs. E1	0.85	1	0.357	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	E2	8196.82	2330	E1 vs. E2	0.83	1	0.363	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	E3	8197.39	2331	E2 vs. E3	0.58	1	0.448	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14	E4	8198.07	2332	E3 vs. E4	0.68	1	0.409	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	E5	8198.57	2333	E4 vs. E5	0.49	1	0.482	Yes
Social Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)								
Final Latent Mean Model								
5-6 = 7-8	FF	8195.48	2328	—	—	—	—	—
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	F1	8197.65	2329	FF vs. F1	2.17	1	0.140	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	F2	8197.70	2330	F1 vs. F2	0.05	1	0.821	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14	F3	8197.70	2331	F2 vs. F3	0.00	1	0.956	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	F4	8198.28	2332	F3 vs. F4	0.58	1	0.447	Yes
	F5	8198.98	2333	F4 vs. F5	0.70	1	0.402	Yes
Advocacy Activities (Bonferroni Correction = .01/5 = .002)								
Final Latent Mean Model								
5-6 = 7-8	FG	8194.52	2328	—	—	—	—	—
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10	G1	8197.76	2329	FG vs. G1	3.24	1	0.072	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12	G2	8202.69	2330	G1 vs. G2	4.93	1	0.026	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14	G3	8202.85	2331	G2 vs. G3	0.16	1	0.688	Yes
5-6 = 7-8 = 9-10 = 11-12 = 13-14 = 15-16	G4	8203.80	2332	G3 vs. G4	0.95	1	0.329	Yes
	G5	8203.88	2333	G4 vs. G5	0.08	1	0.779	Yes

Note. RMSEA, CFI, and TLI did not change from the Strong model in Table 3, or changed by less than .001 across all estimated models.

Table 6
Latent Means, Variances, and Standard Deviations

Support Needs	5–10 Age Group			11–16 Age Group		
	Mean	Variance	SD	Mean	Variance	SD
Home Life	1.80	0.92	0.96	1.27	0.92	0.96
Community and Neighborhood	2.33	1.10	1.05	1.96	1.10	1.05
School Participation	2.30	0.87	0.94	1.88	0.87	0.94
School Learning	3.06	0.54	0.74	2.86	0.54	0.74
Health and Safety	2.25	1.16	1.08	1.97	1.16	1.08
Social	2.23	1.00	1.00	1.89	1.00	1.00
Advocacy	2.34	1.00	1.00	2.23	1.00	1.00

Note. Adapted from the *Catalan SIS-C Users' Manual* by A. L. Adam, D. Simó, J. Mas, M. Dalmau, C., Giné, H. Seo, L. A. Shaw, K. A. Shogren, and J. R. Thompson, 2016. Technical properties of the *Supports Intensity Scale – Children's Version – Catalan Translation*.

across age groups. The differences were concentrated in the latent means. Similar to research on the Spanish Translation (Verdugo et al., 2016), the primary differences were between children ages 6–10 and 11–16. This differs, however, from research with the original U.S. norming sample (Shogren et al., 2015) that found differences in each of the age bands (5–6, 7–8, 9–10, 11–12, 13–14, 15–16). Although the distinctions between Catalonia and Spain discussed previously are important to acknowledge, it is likely that the Spanish and Catalan samples are more similar and share more cultural experiences compared to the U.S. sample. Moreover, compared to the diverse U.S. population, the Spanish and Catalan samples are more homogeneous as demonstrated by the limited differences in the variances and standard deviations across age groups. Differences related to culture and diversity may explain why the age differences were concentrated in younger and older children in the Spanish and Catalan samples, and why this differs from the U.S. sample. However, limitations related to the smaller sample size in the Catalan and Spanish samples, as compared to the U.S. sample, must be considered in interpreting these findings. Further research is needed to explore age-related differences across cultural contexts.

A factor to consider in future research is that there are unique features of primary and secondary education in Catalonia and Spain that might provide insight into the differences from the U.S. sample. In Catalonia, in particular, when students turn 11, they have to move to a secondary education school, and this school is always in a different building from the primary school. Also,

the organization culture of secondary school is highly different than that in primary education, and leads to more distinct differences in experiences for students with intellectual disability. In primary education, the student always has a teacher throughout the academic year; in high school the student has one teacher per subject; the relationship with teachers in primary school is designed to be more supportive and nurturing, whereas the focus shifts in secondary school to identifying each student's future trajectory and providing more standardized curriculum. For students with intellectual disability, particularly those educated in segregated settings, there is less of a focus on promoting access to the general education curriculum, although this remains, in policy, a strong focus in the United States. Further, the lack of consistency in when the transition from primary to secondary school occurs in the U.S. and the explicit focus in Catalonia about the differing purposes of primary and secondary school perhaps leads to a more clear demarcation between the experiences of 6-10 and 11-16 year olds. Future research is needed, however, on the impacts of the shift from primary to secondary school in the Catalonia context and the support needs of children. In combination with the profound changes children experience in the moving from preadolescence to early adolescence (e.g., biological transformation [i.e., puberty], the transition from elementary to secondary schooling), the two age bands (i.e., 5–10 and 11–16) may explain these differences in the Catalonia context, although further research is needed.

These findings have implications that must be considered with regard to support needs assess-

ment in the Catalonia context. First, it will be critical to assess support needs more frequently as children transition to preadolescence and to secondary school as this is the time when differences in support needs are likely to emerge during the developmental period. Future research is needed to examine potential contextual factors that influence these changes, and to explore these factors across cultural contexts. For example, more work is needed to explore differences and similarities across and within Catalonia and Spain that are distinct from the United States. Research is also needed that more precisely examines the presence of intellectual disability, particularly as this was not confirmed in many of the participants in the study given the lack of school records of diagnostic testing in Catalonia. This was a limitation of this study that must be examined in future research. And, research is also needed examining other European and non-European countries. These findings provide direction for future cross-cultural examinations of differences and similarities in support needs, and highlight the need to examine the factors that influence these differences, and changes in support needs during the developmental period. Future research is also needed that examines factors within countries that impact support needs, such as where children live (residential settings vs. home), are educated (inclusive vs. segregated schools), diagnostic information (level of intellectual and adaptive behavior functioning). Such information can inform efforts to move beyond only assessing support needs to using assessment information to plan for systems of support that enable participation in age appropriate, personally valued settings, no matter where those settings might be.

This study shows that Catalonian children ages 6 to 10 and 11 to 16 years differed in terms of the intensity of support needed, and planning teams will need to be cognizant of these differences as they are building systems of supports, considering both intensity of support need, as defined by type, time, and frequency of support, as well as developmental factors and child-level preferences. Any “system of supports” identified and arranged to provide opportunities for full participation in culturally valued settings and activities must be aligned with cultural and social expectations based on age. Future investigations that offer insight into ways in which planning teams can work to address both quantitative and qualitative differences in support needs

is needed across cultural contexts, as is further research that more systematically examines variables within and across cultures that influence support needs.

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